

MANUFACTURING OF Z-PINNED COMPOSITE LAMINATES

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SUMMARY

Z-pinning technique is one of the methods to enhance inter-laminar strength of laminated composites. In this paper general z-pinning technology will be introduced and new concept recently invented by author will be also introduced. The performance in impact resistance of some trial specimens manufactured using the new concept will be investigated.

Keywords: Composite laminates, Z-pinning, Inter-laminar strength, Impact

1. INTRODUCTION

Many techniques including 3D weaving, stitching and braiding have been developed to enhance inter-laminar strength of laminated composites. However, z-pinning is the only technique which can be applied to prepreg laminates. If the other techniques are used to prepreg materials, probably it might result in excessive fibre damage that degrades in-plane mechanical properties. This is a serious limitation because presently many highly loaded composite components, including many aircraft structures, are made using prepreg laminates [1, 2].

In 1989, the first z-pinning concept as shown in Fig. 1 was registered as a USA patent [3] which was known to be originated from Russian research [2]. In this concept they use a kind of foam material called 'pre-form' which is partially collapsible and contains z-pins to be inserted in laminates. Upper part of the pre-form placed on the laminated prepregs is easily collapsed by curing pressure inside autoclave, so the z-pins are inserted to the laminated prepregs during autoclave curing process.

Fig. 1 First z-pinning concept.

After the inserting of the z-pins, the compacted pre-form and the remained part of the z-pins over upper surface of the z-pinned laminates are removed by cutter. However this concept has not been known to be applied in real structure.

In 1996, another concept using ultrasonic tool like Fig. 2 was patented in USA [4] and the concept was actually applied to real aircraft structural joints.

Fig. 2 Typical pre-form and z-pinning concept using ultrasonic horn.

In this concept, they use also the 'pre-form' but they do inserting process of z-pins outside of autoclave just after laminating of prepregs before autoclave curing process. Usually prepreg before curing is very sticky in room temperature, so in order to insert the pins into prepreg without damage of reinforced fibres in prepreg, a very special tool is needed like ultrasonic horn with 20 kHz, very high frequency vibration. It is known that inserting process needs generally 3 to 4 sec, typically producing a square inch of pinned area. With fully automated equipment, point-to-point moves can be made in around 10 sec [5]. After this inserting process and removing of remained part of the pre-form and z-pins, the z-pinned laminated prepregs is cured in autoclave.

Diameter of the z-pin is usually 0.2~1.0mm, and volume ratio of the pin is 0.5~4.0%. Only a relatively small volume fraction of z-pins is needed to significantly enhance the through-thickness properties and damage tolerance. But the only current aerospace application of z-pins is in the F/A-18E/F Super Hornet, which is used to replace titanium fasteners in the air inlet ducts and engine bay doors. This provides a good cost saving (US\$83,000) and modest weight reduction (17 kg) per aircraft [1].

2. NEW Z-PINNING CONCEPT

Recently authors invented a new z-pinning concept as shown in Fig. 3 [6]. In this concept, instead of using the 'pre-form' including z-pins, two parts of repeatedly usable fixtures are used. In the upper fixture, many guide pins are installed permanently in normal direction at lower surface of it. In the lower fixture, many holes are machined and z-pins to be inserted to the laminates are placed inside the holes. In autoclave processing, curing pressure pushes the upper fixture toward lower fixture and the guide pins of upper fixture pushes the z-pins placed inside the holes of the lower fixture to the laminated prepregs. Then the z-pins are inserted into laminated prepregs and finally excessive resin is flow out from the laminated prepregs since the length of the z-pins is just fit for the thickness of normally cured laminate without z-pinning.

Fig. 3 New concept of z-pinning.

This new concept has some advantages in comparison to the upper mentioned existing concepts, i.e. this concept does not need any disposable material like 'pre-form' because the fixtures can do the role of the pre-form and can be used repeatedly. Only z-pins to be inserted needed to be replaced in the holes of lower fixture after finish of curing of a z-pinned composite structure. There is no waste of material at all. As well as this advantage, this concept has another advantage that it can be applied with almost no change of traditionally established autoclave curing procedure. Only an additional simple work is needed to put a couple of fixtures on the laminated prepregs like a curl plate. Inserting process proceeds automatically during curing process in autoclave. So this concept is very compatible with mass production of z-pinned composite structures.

Fig. 4 shows an example of the fixtures manufactured by authors and a typical specimen preliminarily cured using this new concept. Left fixture is upper fixture in which the guide pins are installed to push the z-pins in holes of lower fixture. Right fixture is lower fixture in which many holes are machined.

In order to compare damage tolerance performance of the z-pinned specimen, low-velocity impact test was performed. We can see z-pinned area in central rectangular part of the specimen and local damage induced by the low-velocity impact test at the centre of it.

Fig. 4 The z-pinning fixture and a typical z-pinned specimen using the new concept.

Fig. 5 and 6 show the contact force histories by low-velocity impact test on the preliminarily cured z-pinned specimens and normal specimens. Left figures of Fig. 5 and 6 show contact force history of normal specimens without z-pinning and right figures of Fig. 5 and 6 show contact force history of z-pinned specimens. Fig. 5 is for 3J impact energy and Fig. 6 is for 4J impact energy.

From these two figures it can be seen that contact force history curves of normal specimens show more serious fluctuation. Usually it means more damage may happen in the specimen during contact process by impact. Relatively contact force history curves of z-pinned specimens show less fluctuation. So it can be guessed that less damage might happen in the z-pinned specimen.

Fig. 5 The contact force histories of normal (left) specimen and z-pinned (right) specimen under 3J impact energy test.

Fig. 6 The contact force histories of normal (left) specimen and z-pinned (right) specimen under 4J impact energy test.

Fig. 7 Typical C-scanned impact damage area of normal (left) specimen and z-pinned (right) specimen under 3J impact energy test.

Fig. 8 Typical C-scanned impact damage area of normal (left) specimen and z-pinned (right) specimen under 4J impact energy test.

Fig. 7 and 8 show the C-scanned damage areas after low-velocity impact test on the preliminarily cured z-pinned specimens and normal specimens. Left figures of Fig. 7 and 8 show C-scanned damage areas of normal specimens without z-pinning and right figures of Fig. 7 and 8 show C-scanned damage areas of z-pinned specimens. Fig. 7 is for 3J impact energy and Fig. 8 is for 4J impact energy.

From these two figures it can be surely seen that less damage happened in the z-pinned specimens as expected through comparing of fluctuation of their contact force history curves in Fig. 5 and 6.

3. CONCLUSION

Authors invented a new z-pinning concept. The new concept does not need any disposable materials but only needs repeatedly usable fixture system. It can be applied to the traditional procedure of autoclave curing procedure with almost no change except for putting the fixture system on the laminated prepregs like a curl plate. So this new concept is very useful to apply mass production of z-pinned laminate composite structures.

Applying the new z-pinning concept preliminary fixture system was manufactured and some trial specimens were cured. Low-velocity impact test was performed on the specimens and contact force histories and damage areas were measured. Contact force histories from the z-pinned specimen had less fluctuation than normal specimen, which means less damage happened in z-pinned specimens. From C-scanning results it was surely visualized that z-pinned laminates has better performance in damage tolerance than normal laminates without z-pinning.

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